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TO THE ISSUE OF MALIGNANCY OF ORAL LEUKOPLAKIA

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ABSTRACT

Leukoplakia refers to an optional precancerous disease characterized by varying degrees of keratinization of the surface epithelium, and the rate of malignant transformation of leukoplakia varies widely. In general, the nature of untreated precancerous leukoplakia with a high degree of probability can be considered a sign of malignancy.

Keywords: leukoplakia, markers, proteins, malignization, precancer, cancer

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К ВОПРОСУ О ЗЛОКАЧЕСТВЕННОСТИ ЛЕЙКОПЛАКИИ ПОЛОСТИ РТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Лейкоплакия относится к факультативному предраковому заболеванию, характеризующемуся различной степенью ороговения поверхностного эпителия, а скорость злокачественной трансформации лейкоплакии широко варьирует. В целом характер нелеченой предраковой лейкоплакии с большой долей вероятности можно считать признаком злокачественности.

Ключевые слова: лейкоплакия, маркеры, белки, малигнизация, предрак, рак.

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OG'IZ BOSHLIGI LEYKOPLAKIYASINI MALIGNIZATSIYASIGA OID SAVOLLAR

ANNOTATSIYA

Leykoplakiya sirt epiteliysining turli darajadagi keratinizatsiyasi bilan tavsiflangan ixtiyoriy prekanserov kasallikka ishora qiladi va leykoplakiyaning malign transformatsiya tezligi juda katta farq qiladi. Umuman olganda, yuqori ehtimollik darajasi bilan davolanmagan prekanserov leykoplakiyaning tabiati malignite belgisi sifatida qaralishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: leykoplakiya, markerlar, oqsillar, malignizatsiya, prekanser, saraton.

Introduction. Leukoplakia refers to facultative precancerous diseases, characterized by varying degrees of keratinization of the integumentary epithelium, and the frequency of tumor transformation of leukoplakia varies widely - from 15 to 75% [1].

One of the important molecular markers of malignancy in areas of the oral mucosa with leukoplakia is the determination of DNA ploidy in biopsy specimens using cytological densitometry. As is known, violation of DNA ploidy in cells is one of the important criteria for tissue malignancy. It has been shown that in precancerous lesions of the oral mucosa (leukoplakia and lichen planus) and in cells with dysplasia, the DNA content (aneuploidy) is always increased, while only diploidy is observed in normal epithelial cells [2].

Another sign of neoplastic tissue transformation is a violation of the mechanisms of regulation of apoptosis (programmed cell death) - one of the important (if not the most important) causes of the development of a malignant process [3, 4, 5, 6].

The mechanism of regulation of normal apoptosis is extremely complex, since it is determined by a delicate balance between the enhancement and inhibition of the biosynthesis of many proteins both inside and on the cell surface [7, 8, 9, 10].

Among the many regulators of apoptosis, the survivin protein, which inhibits apoptosis, is important. In most tumors, an increased expression of this protein was found, which may indicate the high information content of survivin as an indicator of neoplasia. In areas of the oral mucosa with signs of precancer, but without malignancy, increased expression of survivin was found only in 33% of cases. At the same time, during the development of cancer in these areas, increased expression of survivin was found in 100% of cases, and in mucosal areas with precancer, from which squamous cell carcinoma developed, in 94% of cases [1].

The authors of the study believe that high expression of survivin in the cytoplasm and nucleus of cells is an early sign of oral mucosal carcinogenesis and may indicate a high risk of precancer progression to invasive carcinoma [10].

Methylation of genes by exogenous agents leads to a significant disruption in the expression of these genes [2], therefore, a change in the number of methylated genes may be an important sign of malignant transformation of oral mucosal cells in tobacco smokers or chewers, since many components of tobacco are active methylating agents [3].

Changes in the expression of the p53 gene are found in cells with signs of malignancy; therefore, the production of the p53 protein in tissues with suspected cancer development can be an important molecular marker of precancerous conditions [4].

Using molecular diagnostic methods, it was shown that in about 90% of cases of biopsies of the oral mucosa from the affected areas, the content of the p53 protein was changed. It has recently been shown that in addition to the main p53 oncogene, there are several more homologous genes whose products control the synthesis of isomorphic alternative splicing proteins. The proteins of these homologous p53 genes are extremely important for cell cycle and proliferation. The two main isoforms of the p63 gene proteins, TAP63 and delta-Np63 proteins, have opposite functions: the TAP63 protein is involved in the mechanism of cell cycle interruption, and the delta-Np63 protein is important for cell proliferation [5].

Immunochemical determination of the production of these proteins in cells of the oral mucosa with squamous carcinoma revealed that the production of both proteins was increased in carcinoma cells compared to unaltered mucosal cells [5].

Moreover, during metastasis of malignant cells, other isoforms of the p63 gene proteins begin to be synthesized in them, and an increase in the synthesis of various isoforms of the proteins of this gene may indicate a poor prognosis for the development of metastases. The expression of another gene - TP73, which is also homologous to the p53 gene, changes with malignancy of epithelial dysplasia of the oral mucosa. These changes may be associated with differentiation of the squamous epithelium, indicate early manifestations of carcinogenesis, and serve as one of the early tests of poor prognosis of epithelial dysplasia of oral mucosal lesions [6].

Another of the homologous p53 genes, the p53R2 gene, encodes the synthesis of a protein that is involved in the repair of DNA molecules. Yamamoto et al . (2003) showed that p53R2 gene expression is extremely important for the oral mucosa, and an increase in its expression can indicate both dysplasia and squamous cell carcinoma: p53R2 expression was not found in any of the 10 samples of normal mucosal epithelium, and in 21% of dysplasia samples and 52% of squamous cell carcinoma samples, the expression of this gene was increased [7].

At the same time, it is not entirely clear why the expression of the p53R2 gene should be determined if the expression of the main p53 oncogene also changes similarly. As is known, for the normal functional activity of cells during proliferative processes, there is a system for regulating the biosynthesis of a number of cytoskeletal proteins, and a violation of the biosynthesis of such proteins is one of the signs of malignancy. An important and rather early indicator of the risk of malignancy of foci of leukoplakia of the oral mucosa is an increase in the expression of about 18 genes of the molecular components of the cytoskeleton in the cells of such a mucosa, which is even higher than in squamous cell carcinoma [8].

For example, during cell malignancy and subsequent invasion of cancer cells, the matrix metalloprotease-9 (MMP-9) gene begins to be expressed in them, and the plasminogen activator is involved in the conversion of the MMP-9 proenzyme into an active metalloproteinase. urokinase type (uPA) [9].

The response of most cells to a stressful situation (in the broad sense of the word) is usually associated with an increase in the biosynthesis of heat shock proteins, especially HSP70. Surprisingly, HSP70 biosynthesis in oral mucosal leukoplakia cells is significantly higher than in lichen planus cells, which are subject to significantly greater morphological transformation [10].

The authors of the data obtained explain this difference in the biosynthesis of HSP70 by the greater activity of proliferative processes in the foci of leukoplakia than in the foci of lichen planus. In patients with squamous cell carcinoma, starting from stage II of the disease, the content of glycosylated proteins changes not only in the tumor cells themselves, but also in the blood and in the erythrocyte membranes. Moreover, the content of glycosylated of conjugates in the blood serum and tumor tissue in such patients with squamous cell carcinoma increases in proportion to the stage of the disease, while their content in erythrocyte membranes, on the contrary, decreases [1].

This may be another confirmation of the systemic disturbances in the body in case of leukoplakia of the oral mucosa. Precancerous conditions of the oral mucosa are etiologically and biologically related to the primary tumor, which is most often sensitive to retinoids. This is the reason for the widespread use of retinoids as therapeutic agents in the treatment of cancerous diseases of the mucosa, not only of the oral cavity [2].

Retinoids are known to modulate the levels of p53 mRNA and protein biosynthesis in tumor cells. Interestingly, a direct correlation has been found between p53 protein levels and retinoid resistance. malignant cells of the oral mucosa, but the mechanism of such a relationship is not entirely clear. At the same time, it has been shown that tobacco carcinogenic factors act not as mutagens, but as methylating factors directly in retinoid receptor genes in mucosal cells, which leads to inhibition of the expression of these receptors [2].

It is assumed that alcohol also acts on the system of retinoids and their receptors, although this action is expressed differently in the metabolism of retinoids and their cellular receptor isoforms. The main sites of alcohol "sabotage" are changes in the enzymatic systems of retinoid metabolism (primarily cytochrome P450 systems) and inhibition of the expression of retinoid receptor isoforms, although the exact mechanisms of action of alcohol are unknown [2].

However, the above is enough to understand the significantly synergistic effect of smoking and alcohol on the mucous membrane of the respiratory and digestive tract. Changes in cell permeability, which is known to depend on the lipid composition of cell membranes, play an important role in the mechanisms of tumorigenesis. The permeability of the membranes of the cells of the oral mucosa in patients with leukoplakia is higher compared to the cells of the normal mucosa. At the same time, in patients with leukoplakia, the total quantitative content of lipids and the qualitative lipid composition of the membranes of both unaltered mucosal cells and cells in areas with leukoplakia differ from the lipid composition of the cells of the normal oral mucosa [3]. In tumor cells of the oral mucosa, the content of total and esterified cholesterol is noticeably higher than in normal cells of the oral mucosa, while the content of free fatty acids and phospholipids, on the contrary, is markedly reduced [4].

Moreover, the same researchers found a significant decrease in the concentration of the main endogenous antioxidant - vitamin E in malignant cells compared with unchanged cells of the oral mucosa. The importance of normal biosynthesis of membrane lipids for cells of the oral mucosa was confirmed by original experiments in cell cultures using cerulenin, a protein that is involved in the regulation of the biosynthesis of a number of membrane lipids: the more significant the disturbances in the composition of the cell membrane, the more cerulenin inhibits the biosynthesis of fatty acids. Moreover, Guo et al. (2003) showed that cerulenin significantly inhibits fatty acid biosynthesis in squamous carcinoma cells and has almost no effect on fatty acid biosynthesis in normal mucosal cells [6].

For the processes of oxidation-reduction in cells, the activity of glutathione -S- transferase (GST), the gene of which is polymorphic, is extremely important. When the oral mucosa is exposed

to various exogenous compounds (tobacco, alcohol, etc.), the activity of different GST isoforms changes differently. Sikdar et al. (2004) showed that among the four GST isoforms, only the GSTM3 (A/A) genotype in tobacco smokers indicates an increased risk of leukoplakia transformation into a malignant neoplasm [7].

In this regard, the determination of the genotype of GST isoforms is proposed by the authors as a molecular marker of malignancy in leukoplakia of the oral mucosa. As you know, invasiveness malignant cells are associated with a violation of the adhesive properties and adhesion mechanisms for such cells. Cell adhesion is largely due to the presence on the cell surface of complex proteins of the cadherin family - transmembrane glycoproteins with a mass of about 120 kDa. A number of researchers believe that impaired expression of cadherins is closely related to carcinogenesis. For squamous cell carcinoma of the oral mucosa, a dysregulation of cadherin P expression has been shown. A decrease in the expression of this transmembrane glycoprotein or its complete absence indicates the aggressiveness of carcinoma cells in terms of their invasiveness and a poor prognosis for such patients [7].

The expression of another adhesion protein, moesin, which is involved in intercellular interaction, also changes. Usually, in normal mucosal cells, moesin is found only on their surface. It has been shown that, in contrast to cells of normal mucosa, in which moesin is found on the outer surface of the membranes, in cells of squamous carcinoma of the oral mucosa, this protein is found only in the cytoplasm [8].

At the same time, the content of the matrix protein, hyaluronan, which is supposed to be a promoter of growth and migration of cancer cells, also changes dramatically in squamous carcinoma cells. Moreover, in poorly differentiated tumors, the content of this protein is markedly reduced, which is a poor prognosis for the survival of patients with this disease [9].

A sign of early progression of pathological cells of the oral mucosa may also be a violation of the expression of cyclin-dependent kinases, which play an important role in the regulation of the cell cycle. Thus, the production of one of the proteins of this type, the p21 protein, increases during proliferation, and the production of the p27 protein increases during cell differentiation, which indicates a fine regulation of the cell cycle processes involving these kinases, and a violation of the ratio in their activity can be an important criterion for signs of mucosal carcinogenesis membranes of the oral cavity [10].

Epidermal growth factor receptors (EGFR) can also be referred to as early markers of neoplastic transformation in the oral mucosa [1]. In the early stages of malignancy of squamous cell carcinoma of the oral mucosa, EGFR expression significantly increases, and the time since the onset of malignancy is proportional to the overexpression of this important protein on the surface of cell membranes [3].

Other proteins, the laminin family, which are synthesized in the basement membranes of the oral mucosa cells, can also be early markers of malignant transformation of the oral mucosa. It has been shown that an increase in the expression of one of the family of these proteins, laminin-5-gamma-2, in damaged areas of the oral mucosa, as a rule, indicates a high risk of malignancy of lesions [3].

Violation of the biosynthesis of a number of collagen proteins, which are important for the adhesion of keratinocytes and their mobility, as a rule, also indicates a violation of the mechanisms of cell adhesion. In invasive forms of malignant transformation of the epithelium of the oral mucosa, the expression of one of the forms of collagen proteins, collagen XVII, begins to increase, and an increase in the expression of this protein may indicate early signs of tumor progression, while the expression of other proteins may still not be disturbed [4].

At the same time, a decrease in the expression of collagen XVII in the early stages of mucosal carcinogenesis may indicate a violation of the mechanisms of adhesion of kerocytes to the basement membrane, and in this case, not only the expression, but also the functions of other proteins related to the mechanisms of adhesion and migration of keratinocytes are likely to be impaired. [4, 5].

In the presence of areas of leukoplakia in the oral cavity, the prognosis of the disease largely depends on which part of the oral mucosa the lesion is located. So, leukoplakia in the areas of the

cheeks and adjacent areas of the mucosa in 96% of cases is a benign formation. In contrast, only about 32% of the mucosal area with leukoplakia under the tongue may be benign, while 31% of the area is carcinoma in situ and 37% - invasive carcinoma [11]. Other areas of the oral mucosa may also show a high degree of malignancy, especially in candidal leukoplakia and leukoplakia, which is clinically characterized by gray or white plaques: in 7-13% of such cases of oral leukoplakia, progression to carcinoma is observed. In general, from the point of view of the nature of precancerous conditions, untreated leukoplakia can most likely be considered a sign of malignancy.

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